

Protocol

This protocol is being reported in compliance with the PRISMA-P (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols) 2015 checklist.[1] It is written in accordance with the *JBIManual for Evidence Synthesis's* guidelines for systematic reviews of etiology and risk.[2]

Section 1: Administrative Information

Title

Environmental toxins and in vitro fertilization (IVF) outcomes: a protocol for a systematic review

Registration

This protocol was registered with a Generalized Systematic Review Registration on the Open Science Framework (OSF) on July 8, 2024.

Registration DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YPBZQ>.

DOI

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Contributions: K.P. is the guarantor, drafted the protocol, and developed the study concept, search strategy, eligibility criteria, and data extraction and risk of bias assessment procedures and forms.

Amendments

Future amendments will be stated here along with the date of the modification and the rationale behind it. K.P. will manage the amendment process in the event that it is needed.

Support

This systematic review has no sponsors or sources of financial or other support.

Section 2: Introduction

Some aspects of human fertility are on the decline. In males, there has been a decrease in semen quality. From 1973 to 2018, sperm concentrations have decreased by 51.6%.^[3] In females, the risk of pregnancy loss has increased.^[4] It is estimated that 17.5% of people have experienced infertility (failure to conceive after a year or more of regular unprotected intercourse) in their lifetime.^[5] Potentially associated with these changes are environmental toxins, many of which have been shown to adversely affect the reproductive system. Environmental toxins are substances linked to health harm. This review will focus on environmental toxins affecting the reproductive system. Various environmental toxins have been linked to issues like lower sperm and egg quality, sex hormone disruptions, infertility, and pregnancy loss, and people are frequently exposed to these chemicals.^[6,7]

With these fertility issues, many couples have turned to assisted reproductive technologies (ART), such as in vitro fertilization (IVF), to have children.^[8] In IVF, the growth of multiple egg follicles is triggered, eggs are harvested from the ovaries, and eggs and sperm are combined in vitro before embryos are transferred to the uterus.^[8] IVF usage is increasing - the number of IVF cycles performed in Europe more than quintupled from 1997 to 2019, making it important to understand potential factors affecting outcomes.^[9] Knowledge concerning how environmental toxins may impact IVF success would inform people undergoing IVF and their healthcare providers. There has not yet been research analyzing the impact of environmental toxins as a whole (rather than specific toxins) on IVF. This kind of research would synthesize existing information into a “summary” that could be used by these IVF patients and healthcare providers, as well as other researchers interested in environmental toxins’ effects. Thus, this systematic review is being conducted to investigate if and how exposure to environmental toxins affects IVF outcomes.

The review question is: does environmental toxin exposure affect IVF outcome, and if so, how?

We conducted a preliminary search in PubMed, Semantic Scholar, PROSPERO, and Google Scholar for previous systematic reviews on the link between exposure to environmental toxins and IVF outcomes. Although there were some studies analyzing the effects of particular kinds of environmental toxins on IVF, none were found that included all environmental toxins, which this review will do.^[10-12]

Section 3: Methods

This protocol’s methodology was designed in accordance with the *JBIM Manual for Evidence Synthesis*’s guidelines for systematic reviews of etiology and risk.^[2]

Eligibility Criteria

Population

We will include studies researching humans undergoing IVF as well as their cells and reproductive organs.

Exposure

Studies analyzing one or multiple environmental toxins or categories of environmental toxins will be included.

Outcome

All outcomes related to IVF success will be included. This may include effects on the reproductive systems or reproductive cells of people undergoing IVF that may impact IVF outcome. Examples of potential outcomes include incidence of successful fertilization, sex cell quality, incidence of successful embryo implantation, incidence of pregnancy loss, etc. Outcomes and their definitions will be extracted as reported by the study.

Timing

There will be no restrictions based on timeframes for follow-up.

Setting

There will be no restrictions based on setting.

Study Design

Opinion articles, perspectives, and editorials will be excluded. All other study designs will be included.

Geographical Location

There will be no restrictions based on location.

Publication Status

There will be no restrictions based on publication status.

Study Year

There will be no restrictions based on year of study execution or publication.

Language

Studies in all languages will be included. If studies not originally in English are found, they will be translated into English using Google Translate.

Information Sources

PubMed, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), SpringerLink (Springer Nature), and Semantic Scholar will be searched. To identify relevant grey literature, OAlster (WorldCat Discovery), medRxiv, and bioRxiv will be searched. To ensure all relevant studies are found, the references of included studies will be searched for additional studies meeting the eligibility criteria that database searching did not identify. If any additional search keywords are identified in any new studies found, the search will be repeated with these keywords. In addition, five included studies' authors will be contacted by email to inquire about any relevant current research or studies that have not yet been published. PubMed, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Semantic Scholar, OAlster, medRxiv, and bioRxiv are planned to be searched between July 22, 2024 and July 27, 2024 (subject to change).

Search Strategy

PubMed, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Semantic Scholar, OAlster, medRxiv, and bioRxiv will be searched (see Information Sources). The search strategy for each database is detailed in the table below.

Database	Search Term(s)
PubMed	<p>(“toxin*” OR “environmental toxin*” OR “reproductive toxin*” OR “reproductive toxicant*” OR “hormonally active agent*” OR “endocrine disrupting compound*” OR “environmental toxicant*” OR “heavy metal*” OR “toxic metal*” OR “pollutant*” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide*” OR “fungicide*” OR “herbicide*” OR “insect repellent*” OR “insecticide*” OR “rodenticide*” OR “inhalation exposure*” OR “occupational exposure*” OR “environmental exposure*” OR “toxic action*” OR “endocrine disruptor*” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical” OR “hazardous substance*” OR “hazardous chemical” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer*” OR “plasticiser*” OR Air Pollution[Mesh] OR Pesticides[Mesh] OR Environmental Exposure[Mesh] OR Toxic Actions[Mesh] OR Plasticizers[Mesh]) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “in vitro fertilisation” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technolog*” OR “reproductive technolog*” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection*” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic*” OR “assisted reproductive technique*” OR “blastocyst transfer*” OR “embryo transfer*” OR “fertilization* in vitro” OR “test tube fertilization*” OR “fertilisation* in vitro” OR “test tube fertilisation*” OR Fertilization in Vitro[Mesh] OR Embryo Transfer[Mesh] OR Reproductive Techniques, Assisted[Mesh])</p>
ScienceDirect	<p>In Title, abstract or author-specified keywords:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (“toxin” OR “environmental toxin” OR “reproductive toxin” OR “endocrine disruptor”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 2. (“reproductive toxicant” OR “hormonally active agent” OR “endocrine disrupting compound” OR “environmental toxicant”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 3. (“heavy metal” OR “pollutant” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 4. (“insecticide” OR “inhalation exposure” OR “occupational exposure” OR “environmental exposure”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 5. (“pesticide” OR “fungicide” OR “herbicide” OR “insect repellent”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 6. (“toxic action” OR “endocrine disruptor” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 7. (“hazardous substance” OR “hazardous chemical” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology”) 8. (“toxin” OR “environmental toxin” OR “reproductive toxin” OR “endocrine disruptor”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”) 9. (“reproductive toxicant” OR “hormonally active agent” OR “endocrine disrupting compound” OR “environmental toxicant”)

	<p>AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>10. (“heavy metal” OR “pollutant” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>11. (“insecticide” OR “inhalation exposure” OR “occupational exposure” OR “environmental exposure”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>12. (“pesticide” OR “fungicide” OR “herbicide” OR “insect repellent”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>13. (“toxic action” OR “endocrine disruptor” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>14. (“hazardous substance” OR “hazardous chemical” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer”) AND (“reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic”)</p> <p>15. (“toxin” OR “environmental toxin” OR “reproductive toxin” OR “endocrine disruptor”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>16. (“reproductive toxicant” OR “hormonally active agent” OR “endocrine disrupting compound” OR “environmental toxicant”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>17. (“heavy metal” OR “pollutant” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>18. (“insecticide” OR “inhalation exposure” OR “occupational exposure” OR “environmental exposure”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>19. (“pesticide” OR “fungicide” OR “herbicide” OR “insect repellent”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>20. (“toxic action” OR “endocrine disruptor” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>21. (“hazardous substance” OR “hazardous chemical” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer”) AND (“assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro”)</p> <p>22. (“toxin” OR “environmental toxin” OR “reproductive toxin” OR “endocrine disruptor”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>23. (“reproductive toxicant” OR “hormonally active agent” OR “endocrine disrupting compound” OR “environmental toxicant”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p>
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	<p>24. (“heavy metal” OR “pollutant” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>25. (“insecticide” OR “inhalation exposure” OR “occupational exposure” OR “environmental exposure”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>26. (“pesticide” OR “fungicide” OR “herbicide” OR “insect repellent”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>27. (“toxic action” OR “endocrine disruptor” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>28. (“hazardous substance” OR “hazardous chemical” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer”) AND “test tube fertilization”</p> <p>29. “toxic metal” AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technology” OR “reproductive technology” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection”)</p> <p>30. “toxic metal” AND (“ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic” OR “assisted reproductive technique” OR “blastocyst transfer” OR “embryo transfer” OR “fertilization in vitro” OR “test tube fertilization”)</p>
SpringerLink	<p>(“toxin*” OR “environmental toxin*” OR “reproductive toxin*” OR “reproductive toxicant*” OR “hormonally active agent*” OR “endocrine disrupting compound*” OR “environmental toxicant*” OR “heavy metal*” OR “toxic metal*” OR “pollutant*” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide*” OR “fungicide*” OR “herbicide*” OR “insect repellent*” OR “insecticide*” OR “rodenticide*” OR “inhalation exposure*” OR “occupational exposure*” OR “environmental exposure*” OR “toxic action*” OR “endocrine disruptor*” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical*” OR “hazardous substance*” OR “hazardous chemical*” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer*” OR “plasticiser*”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “in vitro fertilisation” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted reproductive technolog*” OR “reproductive technolog*” OR “intracytoplasmic sperm injection*” OR “ICSI” OR “assisted reproductive technic*” OR “assisted reproductive technique*” OR “blastocyst transfer*” OR “embryo transfer*” OR “fertilization* in vitro” OR “test tube fertilization*” OR “fertilisation* in vitro” OR “test tube fertilisation*”)</p>
Semantic Scholar	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. environmental toxins and in vitro fertilization 2. toxins and in vitro fertilization 3. endocrine disruptors and in vitro fertilization 4. reproductive toxins and in vitro fertilization 5. pollutants and in vitro fertilization 6. pesticides and in vitro fertilization
OAIster	<p>(“toxin*” OR “environmental toxin*” OR “reproductive toxin*” OR “reproductive toxicant*” OR “hormonally active agent*” OR “endocrine disrupting compound*” OR “environmental toxicant*” OR “heavy metal*” OR “toxic metal*” OR “pollutant*” OR “air pollution” OR “pesticide*” OR “fungicide*” OR “herbicide*” OR “insect repellent*” OR “insecticide*” OR “rodenticide*” OR “inhalation exposure*” OR “occupational exposure*” OR “environmental exposure*” OR “toxic action*” OR “endocrine disruptor*” OR “EDC” OR “endocrine disrupting chemical*” OR “hazardous substance*” OR “hazardous chemical*” OR “noxae” OR “plasticizer*” OR “plasticiser*”) AND (“IVF” OR “in vitro fertilization” OR “in vitro fertilisation” OR “assisted reproduction” OR “assisted</p>

	reproductive technolog* OR "reproductive technolog*" OR "intracytoplasmic sperm injection*" OR "ICSI" OR "assisted reproductive technic*" OR "assisted reproductive technique*" OR "blastocyst transfer*" OR "embryo transfer*" OR "fertilization* in vitro" OR "test tube fertilization*" OR "fertilisation* in vitro" OR "test tube fertilisation*")
medRxiv and bioRxiv	In Abstract or Title: 1. "endocrine disrupt*" AND "in vitro fertilization" 2. "environmental toxin*" AND "in vitro fertilization" 3. "toxin*" AND "in vitro fertilization" 4. "endocrine disrupt*" AND "assisted reproducti*" 5. "environmental toxin*" AND "assisted reproducti*" 6. "toxin*" AND "assisted reproducti*" 7. "heavy metal*" AND "in vitro fertilization" 8. "pollut*" AND "in vitro fertilization" 9. "heavy metal*" AND "assisted reproducti*" 10. "pollut*" AND "assisted reproducti*"

K.P. developed the search strategy and will conduct the search. An expert in database searching (such as a librarian) and a second researcher are not available. The search will not be peer reviewed.

Study Records

Data Management

Search results will be imported into EndNote. Duplicates will be identified in EndNote. Then, the deduplicated search results will be imported into Rayyan. Deduplication will also be performed in Rayyan to ensure all duplicates have been found. Title and abstract screening will be performed in Rayyan, including labeling of reasons for exclusion. Microsoft Excel will be used as the platform for data collection and risk of bias assessment.

Selection Process

One person, K.P., will perform all stages of screening and will be aware of authors and journals involved. Titles and abstracts of identified studies will be screened using the eligibility criteria. Reasons for exclusion will be noted. Full texts will be retrieved for studies that meet or potentially meet the eligibility criteria. Full texts will be screened to ensure the eligibility criteria are met. If any studies are excluded at this point, reasons for exclusion will also be noted. If it is unclear whether a study meets the eligibility criteria, study authors will be contacted by email for clarification.

Data Collection Process

K.P. will perform data extraction (single reviewer data extraction). A spreadsheet in Microsoft Excel (included) will be used, with columns for study title, author, year, journal, participants being studied (whether humans, cells, or organs are being studied, sample size, age(s), sex(es), countries, and any other relevant information), recruitment procedure, toxin(s) being studied, means of exposure and where the toxin(s) are found (if study reports), methods of exposure data collection (if applicable), study design, methods, outcome(s) of interest and their definitions (including how it is measured if applicable), how confounding variable(s)/covariates were addressed (if applicable), results, conflicts of interest (if applicable), any additional notes,

and dates of data extraction. If any relevant information is not reported, study authors will be contacted by email a maximum of three times to request additional information or clarification. If any duplicate reports are found, data will be extracted once. If there are any inconsistencies between duplicate reports, study authors will be contacted by email for clarification.

Outcomes

All outcomes related to IVF success will be included. This may include effects on the reproductive systems or reproductive cells of people undergoing IVF that may impact IVF outcome. Examples of potential outcomes include incidence of successful fertilization, sex cell quality, incidence of successful embryo implantation, incidence of pregnancy loss, etc. Outcomes and their definitions will be extracted as reported by the study. A more detailed description of outcomes included will be specified in the completed review, after these definitions are known.

Risk of Bias in Individual Studies

Risk of bias assessment and data extraction will be conducted together. One assessor, K.P., will perform quality assessment, as multiple assessors are not available. The assessor will not be blinded to study titles or journals. Risk of bias assessment will be performed for each study. The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) will be used for risk of bias assessment in case control and cohort studies, ToxRTool (Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool) will be used for in vitro studies, and JBI's critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews will be used for systematic reviews.[13-15] Using the NOS, each study will earn up to nine stars, for the categories of selection, comparability, and either exposure or outcome, for case control and cohort studies respectively. Studies with 0 to 5 stars will be considered poor quality, studies with 6 or 7 stars will be considered moderate quality, and studies with 8 or 9 stars will be considered good quality. In the comparability category, we will check that age is controlled for in the study.[16] In the selection category for cohort studies, we will check if the exposed cohort is representative of the average exposed person undergoing IVF. In the outcome category for cohort studies, 20% will be considered a small number of subjects that did not follow up. Using ToxRTool, each study will earn up to 18 points and be assigned a Klimisch reliability categorization based on its number of points. Studies with 15 to 18 points will be assigned "reliable without restrictions," studies with 11 to 14 points will be assigned "reliable with restrictions," and studies with less than 11 points will be assigned "not reliable." Additionally, studies that do not earn a point for certain "red" criteria will be assigned "not reliable." ToxRTool assigns points in the categories of test substance identification, test system characterization, study design description, study results documentation, and plausibility of study design and data. Using JBI's critical appraisal tool, for each "yes" to a question on the checklist, the study will earn one point, for a maximum of eleven points. Studies with 0 to 5 points will be considered poor quality, studies with 6 to 8 points will be considered moderate quality, and studies with 9 to 11 points will be considered good quality. If any modifications to the NOS, ToxRTool, or JBI's critical appraisal tool are needed for particular included studies, these modifications and the rationale behind them will be described in the completed systematic review. A Microsoft Excel spreadsheet (included) will be used for risk of bias assessment. This spreadsheet, completed, will also be included in the final review. Additionally, the Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale document, ToxRTool explanation and assessment spreadsheet, and JBI Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses document that will be used to assess each study are included and will be

in the Appendix in the completed review. Concerns with risk of bias will be discussed with the results of the study when applicable. There will be an additional discussion on conflicts of interest, confounding variables/covariates, and any additional concerns when necessary.

Data Synthesis

A narrative synthesis will be conducted without meta-analysis. Meta-analysis would not be appropriate because studies examining a variety of toxins and a variety of outcomes will be included. Data will be grouped by outcome. Within each of these sections, studies' toxin(s) analyzed, designs and methodologies, participants, results, and risk of bias concerns when applicable will be discussed with text. All studies, regardless of risk of bias, will be discussed, but concerns with risk of bias will be discussed with the results of the study. For each section or set of sections, a summary table with each good quality, moderate quality, "reliable without restrictions," and "reliable with restrictions" study in that section will be provided. This table will include data on each study's design, toxin(s) analyzed, participants, and results. A summary table will also be included for the study as a whole providing information on studies' designs, toxin(s) analyzed, participants, results, and risk of bias. Completed data extraction and risk of bias tables will be included in the Appendix. Information from all studies, regardless of study design, will be reported on in this manner, and no type of study design will be prioritized.

Meta-Bias(es)

To address potential publication bias, five included studies' authors will be contacted by email to inquire about any studies that have not yet been published. To address potential outcome reporting bias, it will be noted if any outcomes are reported in the methods sections of studies that are not reported on in the results.

Confidence in Cumulative Estimate

If there are multiple studies on the same toxin and outcome, the number of each risk of bias categorization and whether the results were consistent will be stated.

Time Frame

If the systematic review takes over six months from the first day of database searching for completion, the search will be repeated to identify any newer, previously unidentified studies before publication.

Conflicts of Interest

The author has no known potential conflicts of interest.

Guidance Sources

The following sources were used as guidance for the development of this protocol and the future systematic review: [1-2,17-43].

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